

A highly efficient synthesis of 3*H*-1,5-benzodiazepine derivatives using lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate as a catalyst

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Abstract : Sulphonation of 5-(2-ethoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one (1) with chlorosulphonic acid affords 5-[(5-chlorosulphonyl-2-ethoxy)pyrimidin]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one (2). Compound (2) condensed with different β -diketones/ β -ketoesters (3a-e) to obtain new β -diketones/ β -ketoesters (4a-e). These β -diketones/ β -ketoesters were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PDA) in presence of lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate to afford biologically active 3*H*-1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-e) in excellent yield. The compounds (5a-e) have been screened for antimicrobial, antifungal and anthelmintic activities.

Keywords : Lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate, 3*H*-1,5-benzodiazepines, β -diketones, β -ketoesters, pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one.

Introduction

Benzodiazepines have attracted attention as an important class of heterocyclic compounds in the field of drugs and pharmaceuticals. These compounds are widely used as anticonvulsant, antianxiety, analgesic, sedative, anti-depressive, hypnotic agents¹ as well as anti-inflammatory agents². Other than their biological importance, benzodiazepines derivatives are also commercially used as dyes for acrylic fibres³. Moreover, 1,5-benzodiazepines derivatives are valuable synthons that can be used in the preparation of other fused ring compounds such as triazolo-, oxadiazolo-, oxazino-, or furano-benzodiazepines⁴. Research in this area is still very active and is directed towards the synthesis of compounds with enhanced pharmacological activity. Generally, these compounds are synthesized by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamines with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds⁵, β -haloketones, or ketones⁶. A variety of reagents, such as BF₃-etherate, NaBH₄, polyphosphoric acid, or SiO₂, MgO/POCl₃, Yb(OTf)₃, Sc(OTf)₃, Al₂O₃/P₂O₅, or AcOH under microwave irradiation and in the presence of ionic liquids⁷ have been utilized for condensation reactions. Most recently, this condensation has also been reported to proceed in the presence of CAN, (bromodimethyl) sulfonium bromide, organic acids, and AgNO₃⁸. However, all of these methods have the common disadvantage of employing drastic reaction condi-

tions and also producing several side products. We report here a new method for the preparation of 1,5-benzodiazepine derivatives with β -diketones and β -ketoesters. It was found that lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate was capable of producing high yields of 1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-e) by condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with dicarbonyl compounds (4a-e) under mild conditions in 70-78% yield.

The present work is focused on the synthesis pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one containing 1,5-benzodiazepines due to importance of this class of compounds which has recently found application in medicinal chemistry. Substituted pyrazolopyrimidinones are potent and selective inhibitors of type 5 cyclic guanosine-3',5'-monophosphate phosphodiesterase(cGMP)PDE-5^{9,10} which have utility in the treatment of male erectile dysfunction (MED)¹¹ and female sexual dysfunction (FSD). They also find use in the treatment of impotence, one of male sexual dysfunction with reduced side effects¹². Substituted pyrazolopyrimidinones are also useful as CNS stimulant, bronchodilator, cardiotonic¹³, herbicide¹⁴ and antiviral¹⁵ agent.

Results and discussion

At first, 5-(2-ethoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one was sulphonated with chlorosulphonic acid, sulphonated compound

(2) was condensed with different β -diketones/ β -ketoesters in the presence of sodium methoxide (Scheme 1). The synthesized β -diketones/ β -ketoesters (4a-e) and *o*-phenylenediamine was condensed in the presence of lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate (Scheme 2), to obtain 3*H*-1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-e). The synthesized com-

pounds are characterized by elemental analysis and spectral data.

Antimicrobial and anthelmintic activities of compounds (5a-e) :

The newly synthesized diazepine compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus*

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

aurens and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* by cup-plate method^{16,17}. Crofloxin and Ciclopirox olamine were used as standards for comparison of antibacterial and antifungal activities, respectively. The results indicate that these compounds were active against all the four organisms. The anthelmintic activity was carried out on earth worms *Pheretima posthuma*, by a technique as described by Bagavant *et al.*¹⁸ with modification. Piperazine citrate was used as standard drug. The results of antimicrobial and anthelmintic activity were showed in Table 2.

Table 1

Entry	R ¹ (4)	R ² (4)	R ¹ (5)	R ² (5)	Yield of 4	Yield of 5
a	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	75.2	78.8
b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	72.1	75.6
c	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	70.3	75.5
d	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	O	73.8	70.3
e	OC ₂ H ₅	OC ₂ H ₅	O	O	74.9	76.2

Note

Table 2. Antimicrobial and anthelmintic activities of compounds (5a-e)

Compd.	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal activity		Anthelmintic activity	
	Zone of inhibition		Zone of inhibition		(min)	
	(mm)		(mm)			
	<i>A. aureus</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	Paralysis	Death
5a	11	12	10	20	87	90
5b	9	9	11	13	101	78
5c	12	8	13	27	80	93
5d	11	9	10	12	86	91
5e	13	7	14	27	78	69
Std	12	7	12	28	89	96

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet-Magna-FT-IR-550 spectrometer in KBr pellets: ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were run on model DRX 300 at 300.13 MHz and 75 MHz respectively in CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a LCMS instrument. The purity of the newly synthesized compounds was checked by TLC. Satisfactory C, H, N analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5-[(5-chlorosulphonyl-2-ethoxy)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (2) :

To a solution of 5-(2-ethoxy phenyl)-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (1) (3.12 g, 0.01 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (100 ml), chlorosulphonic acid (1.17 g, 0.01 mol) was added dropwise at such a rate that temperature maintained at 0 °C. After complete addition, the reaction mass was stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 60 °C for 2 h. The completion of reaction was checked through TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase. After the completion of the reaction, the reaction mass was poured in crushed ice and water. Then it was extracted with dichloromethane and the dichloromethane layer was dried using anhydrous sodium sulphate. The dichloromethane was evaporated so as to get the residual mass. It was then crystallized in methanol. Purity of compound was checked through TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase (m.p. 195 °C, yield 2.8 g, 64%).

General procedure for the synthesis of 5-[2-ethoxy-5(1,3-dimethyl/1,3-diphenyl/1-phenyl-3-methyl/1-methyl-3-

ethoxy/1,3-ethoxy propane-1,3-dione-2-sulphonyl) phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (4a-e) :

Sodium methoxide (0.54 g, 0.01 mol) and β-diketones/β-ketoesters (0.01 mol) were placed in a dry round bottom flask and stirred for one hour on a magnetic stirrer at a temperature of 50 °C, to obtain the sodium salt of β-diketones/β-ketoesters. The sulphonyl chloride derivative (2) (4.1 g, 0.01 mol) was then added and dry toluene was added as solvent to effect proper stirring of the reaction mass. The reaction mixture was heated for about six hours at 80 °C with stirring. The progress of the reaction was monitored through TLC. After reaction was completed, the reaction mass was cooled and toluene was removed under reduced pressure. The reaction mass was extracted using chloroform and then washed with water so as to remove the salt. The chloroform layer was then dried using sodium sulphate. Chloroform was evaporated to get viscous compound. It was crystallized with chloroform and ethyl acetate. Purity of the compounds (4a-e) was checked through TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase (yield 70-75%).

Synthesis of 3H-1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-e) : General procedure :

To a mixture of β-diketones/β-diketoesters (0.01 mol) (4a-e), *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) and lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate (0.01 mol) were added in dichloromethane (50 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at 50 °C for 60 min. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase. The mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2 × 25 ml) and the solvent was

removed and obtained crude product. The crude product was washed with dry ether to remove unreacted β -diketones/ β -ketoesters. The crude product was recrystallized from pet ether : ethyl acetate (1 : 1). The product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using pet ether : ethyl acetate (40 : 60) as eluent.

Spectral data :

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(2,4-dimethyl-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-3-sulphonyl)-phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5a) : Crystalline solid, m.p. 184 °C, yield 78.8%; IR (KBr) : 3320, 3060, 3060, 2960, 1715, 1580, 1330, 1240, 1150, 1030 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.67 Hz), 1.33 (3H, t, *J* 7.13 Hz), 1.35 (3H, s), 1.55 (2H, m), 2.50 (6H, s), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 6.78 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.98 (2H, q, *J* 7.43 Hz), 4.60 (1H, s), 7.2–7.8 (7H, m), 8.73 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 126.31–160.65, 149.96, 75.39, 67.83, 53.27, 40.34, 15.86, 14.70 (Found : C, 61.55; H, 5.50; N, 15.37. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 61.53; H, 5.49; N, 15.38%); HRMS *m/z* : 547.3713 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(2,4-diphenyl-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-3-sulphonyl)-phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5b) : m.p. 235 °C, yield 75.6%; IR (KBr) : 3320, 3060, 3060, 2960, 1715, 1580, 1330, 1240, 1150, 1030 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 8.04 Hz), 1.35 (3H, s), 1.55 (2H, m), 1.57 (3H, t, *J* 8.04 Hz), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 7.54 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.42 (2H, q, *J* 8.04 Hz), 4.60 (1H, s), 7.36–8.4 (17H, m), 8.70 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 126.3–160.6, 149.94, 75.39, 67.87, 40.33, 15.85, 14.7 (Found : C, 68.07; H, 5.05; N, 12.55. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 68.05; H, 5.07; N, 12.53%); HRMS *m/z* : 671.7531 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(1-phenyl-4-methyl-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-3-sulphonyl)-phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5c) : m.p. 216 °C, yield 75.5%; IR (KBr) : 3325, 3060, 3050, 2930, 1655, 1610, 1320, 1150, 1245, 1020 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.66 Hz), 1.35 (3H, s), 1.55 (2H, m), 1.57 (3H, t, *J* 9.17 Hz), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 9.05 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.42 (2H, q, *J* 6.89 Hz), 4.60 (1H, s), 7.36–8.4 (12H, m), 8.70 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 196.59, 164.63, 126.25–160.69, 65.18, 33.73, 24.9, 23.34, 15.69, 13.65 (Found : C, 63.68; H, 5.50; N, 13.70. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 63.73; H,

5.54; N, 13.76%); HRMS *m/z* : 609.9563 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(4-methyl-1,3-dihydro-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-2-one-3-sulphonyl)-phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5d) : m.p. 166 °C, yield 70.3%; IR (KBr) : 3350, 3030, 2950, 1720, 1580, 1345, 1150, 1260, 1020 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.49 Hz), 1.55 (2H, m), 1.57 (3H, t, *J* 7.83 Hz), 2.40 (3H, s), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 8.34 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.42 (2H, q, *J* 8.14 Hz), 7.25–7.86 (7H, m), 8.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 157–128.3, 149.9, 75.3, 68.3, 54.3, 40.3, 29.5, 15.8, 14.6 (Found : C, 58.99; H, 5.31; N, 15.29. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{S}$: C, 59.02; H, 5.46; N, 15.30%); HRMS *m/z* : 549.3810 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(1,5-dihydro-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-2,4-dione-3-sulphonyl)-phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5e) : m.p. 193 °C, yield 76.2%; IR (KBr) : 3320, 3060, 2960, 1715, 1580, 1330, 1240, 1150, 1030 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.56 Hz), 1.55 (2H, m), 1.62 (3H, t, *J* 7.94 Hz), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 7.44 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.28 (1H, s), 4.44 (2H, q, *J* 7.52 Hz), 7.3–7.8 (7H, m), 8.75 (2H, brs); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 165.5, 125.7–157, 149.8, 75.3, 68.3, 54.8, 40.3, 15.8, 14.6 (Found : C, 50.90; H, 5.30; N, 16.15. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 50.86; H, 5.33; N, 16.19%); HRMS *m/z* : 551.3571 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$).

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